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NUMERISATION

NONLINEAR NUMERICAL APPROXIMATIONS OF TRANSPORT COEFFICIENTS AND PHENOMENOLOGICAL COEFFICIENTS GOVERNING THE COCOA DRYING PROCESS

By

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Abstract

Cocoa beans are highly coveted products in the food and cosmetics industries due to their numerous therapeutic properties. These products generally have high humidity or intermediate humidity, hence the importance of their stabilization by drying. Obtaining well-dried cocoa that meets international requirements requires mastery of this process. This paper deals with a numerical strategy based on the Least Square Method for the determination of transportation coefficients and phenomenological coefficients from the non-linear mathematical model which governs the coupled transport of water and acid in a bean cocoa during drying. Our work reveals that the absolute values of D_a , D_{ea} , and D_e are respectively of the order of 10^{-4} , 10^{-6} , and 10^{-8} (Kg/m.s) while the absolute values of K_{aa} , K_{ea} and K_{ee} are of the order of 10^{-8} , 10^{-12} , and 10^{-11} (kg.s.°C/m³). In addition, the transport coefficients and the corresponding phenomenological coefficients have the same direction of variation with respect to time. Numerical simulations are carried out for five tests on conditions (Relative Humidity, Speed, Temperature) accurate.

Keywords: Approximation, nonlinearity, transportation coefficients, phenomenological coefficients, representative average bean, numerical simulation.

1 Introduction

Cocoa beans are seeds of the tropical cocoa tree (see [1]). They have a quality problem, due to too high acetic acid content. Resulting from the fermentation of cocoa and essential for the formation of the aroma, this acid must then be evacuated from the seed (see [2]). The cocoa drying process takes place in 3 phases. The first phase is very short and is

characterized by a gradual increase in temperature of the beans (see [3]). During this phase, the heat allows free water to be quickly evacuated from the beans (pulp and shell), so as to increase the drying kinetics. In the second phase, the temperature of the grains is stabilized because all the drying energy supplied is spent in the evaporation of water. During this stage, the drying front moves from the outer surface of the hull to the interior of the grains and the drying rate remains constant. The last and longest phase is characterized by an increase in product temperature and a decrease in drying speed (see [3] and [4]). For a good understanding of this drying process, multiple efforts have been made for a long time to model the kinetics of drying. Modelling drying kinetics can be carried out using semi-theoretical methods (see for instance [5], [6], [7], [8], [9] and [10]), Fick's theoretical model (see [11] and [12]) and empirical models (see [13]). [14] and [15] also reported the characteristic drying curves of cocoa beans at different external conditions with critical moisture contents identified in their studies. [1] reported the effect of temperature and drying air velocity on the drying rate and drying constant of cocoa beans. Using an indirect solar dryer, the experimental desorption isotherms of cocoa beans, for different temperatures (30, 45, 60 °C) have a sigmoidal appearance (See[16]). The Lewis equation which has been considerably modified (see [17], [18], [19], [20], [21]) provides simple and clear solution to moisture content and temporal relationship in thin layer drying of biomaterials. According to [22], the Lewis equation problem is a high drying rate problem, but a correct prediction of the drying constants can solve this problem. A numerical model of cocoa beans drying kinetics in an indirect solar and air crossing dryer has been developed by [23]. A coupled transport model of water and acid is developed and validated by comparison with experimental results relating to the interior of a "representative average bean" (see [2]). It serves as the basis for a computer simulation program, properly reproducing the experiment and making it possible to identify the key parameters responsible for acid migration. Our work is particularly interested in this last nonlinear mathematical model. Our research objective is to develop from the last model, a strategy for numerical calculation of the phenomenological coefficients and the transport coefficients which govern the coupled transport of water and acid in the cocoa bean during drying in convection mode.

Nomenclatures

σ : source of mass entropy of the system,

T : temperature of the system,

μ_{ai} : mass chemical potential of component i in the phase α

J_{ai}^k : flux of diffusion of component i compared to the solid skeleton,

K_{ee}, K_{aa} : are respectively the phenomenological coefficients of water and acid,

K_{ea}, K_{ae} : the coupled phenomenological coefficients between water and acid,

$\mu_e^0(T), \mu_a^0(T)$: chemical potentials of reference at a given temperature,

R : constant of perfects gas,

M_e, M_a : are respectively molar mass of the water and acid,
 p_e^*, p_a^* : are respectively partial pressure of water and acid vapours at equilibrium,
 D_e : is the apparent coefficient of transport of water,
 D_{ea}, D_{ae} : the apparent coefficient of the transport coupled between water and the acid,
 D_a : the apparent coefficient of transport of the acid.
 ρ_{ai} : the mass of component i in the phase α inside a unit volume

2 Water and Acid transfer

2.1 Isothermal bi-constituent transportation model in a porous environment

An explanatory model of combined diffusion of water and acid in cocoa has been *developed* from irreversible principles of thermodynamic processes. The physical system considered is an idealized cocoa bean made up of porous skeleton in which two constituents, water and acetic acid, can migrate (see [2]).

2.1.1 Simplifying hypotheses

Our physical model of a representative average cocoa bean considers the following hypothesis:

- H1** The temperature is constant and uniform in the entire medium and into all the phases.
- H2** The cocoa broad bean is made up of a porous skeleton in which water and acid can be present in various forms, liquid, gaseous or linked to the solid phase.
- H3** There is a local balance between the various shapes of water and acid.
- H4** The speeds and accelerations of transports are low.
- H5** No chemical reaction develops in broad bean.
- H6** The action of gravity is neglected.
- H7** The evolution of the system is restricted to the neighbourhood of the equilibrium, in other words, the imposed requests do not involve a too strong imbalance.
- H8** The gas phase of the system is regarded as a mixture of perfect gas.
- H9** The interaction between the deformations and the transfers of matter, is reduced to the withdrawal described.

2.1.2 Mass balance equations

Within a cocoa broad bean, the mass balance for water and acid in the state α has the form (see [5]):

$$\frac{\partial \rho_{ai}}{\partial t} = -(\rho_{ai} \cdot V_{ai}^k)_{,k} + r_{ai} \quad (1)$$

In this relation, the left-hand side represents the variations of the mass of component i in the phase α inside a unit volume. Then a diffusive flux of constituent i is used in relation with the movement of the solid skeleton. This movement is supposed to be very slow compared to the movement of the fluids.

$$J_{ai}^k = \rho_{ai} \cdot (V_{ai}^k - V_s^k) = \rho_{ai} \cdot V_{ai}^k \quad (2)$$

2.1.3 Entropy source

Investigations about the entropy source of in heterogeneous media have been the object of several studies (see for instance [24] and [25]). Under the following hypotheses: constant and uniform temperature field (H1); low acceleration and speeds (H4); absence of chemical reactions (H5); and neglecting the gravity effect and terms involving the gradient of pressure tensor, the source of mass entropy of the system is reduced to the diffusion of cocoa components and reads:

$$\sigma = - \sum_{\alpha} \sum_i J_{\alpha i}^k \left(\frac{\mu_{\alpha i}}{T} \right)_{,k} \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

The source of entropy can be interpreted as the sum of the products of thermodynamic powers (water and acid flux). In the case of the Thermodynamics of irreversible processes in the neighbourhood of the equilibrium, we will deduce the phenomenological relation which links powers and fluxes.

2.1.4 Consequences of local thermodynamical equilibrium assumption

Let us consider J_e and J_a the global fluxes of water and acid (respectively) without any distinction of phase. They equal the sum of fluxes in each phase:

$$J_e = J_{se} + J_{le} + J_{ge}; \quad J_a = J_{sa} + J_{la} + J_{ga}$$

In the same way, we get the following relations:

$$\rho_e = \rho_{se} + \rho_{le} + \rho_{ge}; \quad \rho_a = \rho_{sa} + \rho_{la} + \rho_{ga}$$

According to (H5) there is neither creation nor absorption of water or acid. As a consequence, the sum of the input of mass for a constituent in all the phases is null ($r_a = 0$): Summing the mass balance equation (1) corresponding to the phases involving a constituent, utilizing the definition of flux (2) and the preceding notations, leads to:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_e}{\partial t} = - \sum_{\alpha} (\rho_{\alpha e} \cdot V_{\alpha e}^k)_{,k} = - \sum_{\alpha} J_{\alpha e}^k = J_{e,k}^k \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho_a}{\partial t} = - \sum_{\alpha} (\rho_{\alpha a} \cdot V_{\alpha a}^k)_{,k} = - \sum_{\alpha} J_{\alpha a}^k = J_{a,k}^k \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, the hypothesis of local equilibrium (H3) is represented by the equality of the chemical potential in solid, liquid and vapour phase for each component:

$$\mu_{e \text{ solid}} = \mu_{e \text{ oil}} = \mu_{e \text{ gaz}} = \mu_e$$

$$\mu_{a \text{ solid}} = \mu_{a \text{ oil}} = \mu_{a \text{ gaz}} = \mu_a$$

The amalgam of the phases in the material finally leads to a simple expression of the entropy source (3):

$$\sigma = - \left(\frac{\mu_e}{T} \right)_{,k} \cdot J_e^k - \left(\frac{\mu_a}{T} \right)_{,k} \cdot J_a^k \quad (6)$$

2.1.5 Phenomenological relations

Let us assume that the forces and flows appearing in the expression of the entropy source (6) vary linearly according to the thermodynamical forces (field of the Thermodynamics of the linear irreversible processes). In our frame work, the chemical divergence of potentials represents the thermodynamical forces (action causing the phenomenon) and

flows the manifestation of the phenomenon. Setting in the terms of equation, this principle writes:

$$J_e^k = -K_{ee} \left(\frac{\mu_e}{T} \right)_{,k} - K_{ea} \left(\frac{\mu_a}{T} \right)_{,k} \quad (7)$$

$$J_a^k = -K_{ea} \left(\frac{\mu_e}{T} \right)_{,k} - K_{aa} \left(\frac{\mu_a}{T} \right)_{,k} \quad (8)$$

2.1.6 Expressions of chemical potentials

Taking into account the equilibrium hypothesis, the chemical potentials of acid and water can be determined from chemical potentials of the constituents in vapour phase. These potentials in a mixture of supposed perfect gas (H8) can be written as follows:

$$\mu_{e\text{ gaz}} = \mu_e^0(T) + \frac{RT}{M_e} \ln p_e^* = \mu_e$$

$$\mu_{a\text{ gaz}} = \mu_a^0(T) + \frac{RT}{M_a} \ln p_a^* = \mu_a$$

Spatial derivation of these expressions can be written as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\mu_e}{T} \right)_{,k} = \frac{R}{M_e} \frac{p_{e,k}^*}{p_e^*} \quad (9)$$

$$\left(\frac{\mu_a}{T} \right)_{,k} = \frac{R}{M_a} \frac{p_{a,k}^*}{p_a^*} \quad (10)$$

At the thermodynamical equilibrium which is locally assumed, a relationship exists between p_e^* , X and A on the one hand and p_a^* , X and A on the other hand. Hence: $p_e^* = p_e^*(X, A)$, $p_a^* = p_a^*(X, A)$. With these new variables, one deduces:

$$\left(\frac{\mu_e}{T} \right)_{,k} = \frac{R}{M_e p_e^*} \left[\frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial X} X_{,k} + \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial A} A_{,k} \right] \quad (11)$$

$$\left(\frac{\mu_a}{T} \right)_{,k} = \frac{R}{M_a p_a^*} \left[\frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial X} X_{,k} + \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial A} A_{,k} \right] \quad (12)$$

2.1.7 Transport equations

By introducing (11) and (12) in (7) and (8), we obtain the general phenomenological relations:

$$J_e^k = -D_e \cdot X_{,k} - D_{ea} \cdot A_{,k} \quad (13)$$

$$J_a^k = -D_{ae} \cdot X_{,k} - D_a \cdot A_{,k} \quad (14)$$

with

$$D_e = K_{ee} \frac{R}{M_e p_e^*} \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial X} + K_{ea} \frac{R}{M_a p_a^*} \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial X} \quad (15)$$

$$D_{ea} = K_{ee} \frac{R}{M_e p_e^*} \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial A} + K_{ea} \frac{R}{M_a p_a^*} \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial A} \quad (16)$$

$$D_e = K_{aa} \frac{R}{M_a p_a^*} \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial A} + K_{ea} \frac{R}{M_e p_e^*} \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial A} \quad (17)$$

$$D_{ae} = K_{aa} \frac{R}{M_a p_a^*} \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial X} + K_{ea} \frac{R}{M_e p_e^*} \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial X} \quad (18)$$

The relations (13) and (14) constitute the general equations of water and acid transportation in an ideal medium at the sense of the subsection 2.1.1.

2.2 A numerical strategy of calculation of the transport coefficients

2.2.1 Evaluating the transport coefficients and the phenomenological coefficients

Given the flattened shape of cocoa broad bean, it can be assimilated with an infinite plate. We therefore assume that the matter transfer flows in one direction only which is that of the thickness. This direction is called later the x axis. When carrying (13) into (4) (respectively (14) into (5)) and after projecting the result on the x -axis we obtain for water and acid the following relations:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^x \rho_s(X) \cdot X dx = D_e \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + D_{ea} \frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^x \rho_s(X) \cdot A dx = D_{ae} \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + D_a \frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \quad (20)$$

Let us consider

$$m_e = m_e(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^x \rho_s(X) \cdot X dx$$

$$m_a = m_a(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^x \rho_s(X) \cdot A dx$$

$$DPe = DPe(x, t) = \frac{R}{M_e p_e^*} \left[\frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial X} \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial A} \frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \right]$$

$$DPa = DPa(x, t) = \frac{R}{M_a p_a^*} \left[\frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial X} \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial A} \frac{\partial A}{\partial x} \right]$$

while using (7), (8), (13), and (14), we obtain:

$$m_e = K_{ee} DPe + K_{ea} DPa \quad (21)$$

$$m_a = K_{aa} DPa + K_{ea} DPe \quad (22)$$

Considering the hypothesis $D_{ea} = D_{ae}$, and taking into account the relations (21) and (22) we obtain:

$$K_{ea} = \left[m_a \frac{DPe}{M_a p_a^*} \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial X} - m_e \frac{DPa}{M_e p_e^*} \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial A} \right] / \left[\frac{DPe}{M_a p_a^*} \left(DPa \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial A} + DPe \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial X} \right) - \frac{DPa}{M_e p_e^*} \left(DPe \frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial X} + DPa \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial A} \right) \right] \quad (23)$$

and

$$K_{ee} = \frac{m_e - K_{ea} DPa}{DPe} \quad (24)$$

$$K_{aa} = \frac{m_a - K_{ea} DPe}{DPa} \quad (25)$$

2.2.1 Obtaining the smoothed profiles

An experimental profile is made up of five values of water content from the center to the corresponding bean edge of broad bean. In addition, the tests contain between 4 and 7 profiles (generally 5) corresponding to the taking away carried out during drying. The number of points for each test, ranging between 20 and 35, not enough for permitting an accurate calculation of gradient. This is why we use a suitable method of smoothing

allowing to obtain profiles every 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 hours depending on the duration of test, each one of these profiles containing 12 points.

The method is described using the test1 results. Figure 2 shows the evolution of the water content measured during this test, in the 5 slices of half-broad bean. To obtain the exploitable profiles, one carries out 3 successive smoothing. The first is most delicate because it is necessary to consider the maximum of points, while knowing to eliminate those which were the object of handling errors. Given uncertainties on our measures and the experience necessary to analyse the errors, smoothing cannot in any case be carried out by data processing. The experimental profiles are thus smoothed by hand (see Figure 3). One records then the values of water content (measurements on paper using a scale) at x-coordinates 0 (center), 0.2 0.4 , 0.6 , 0.8 and 1 (periphery) of the half-thickness. The second smoothing (see Figure 4), is based on the kinetics of drying obtained from each of these x-coordinates. In test1, drying is continued in a fictitious manner by the means of smoothing: the last smoothed profile is at 27h whereas the test had been stopped after 24h. The water contents are recorded at regular intervals of one hour for short tests and 5 hours for the longer dryings. The third and last smoothing make it possible to multiply the number of calculation points by two, measuring the contents at the x-coordinates 0.1 0.3 0.5 0.7 0.9 and 1.1 of the half-thickness (see Figure 5). x-coordinate 1.1 located outside the broad bean is taken into account in order to measure the gradient of the water content at the edge.

After smoothing of the experimental profiles table $X(x, t)$ contain between 100 and 200 values. They represent the evolution during the drying (variable t) of the profile of water content X, in the seed half-thickness (variable x). A similar work leads to table $A(x, t)$ containing between 100 and 200 values representing the evolution during the drying (variable t) of the profile of acid content A, in the seed half-thickness (variable x). tables $X(x, t)$ and $A(x, t)$ are used as data for the calculation of the coefficients (See [2]).

2.2.3 Numerical calculation of coefficients

The transportation coefficients are calculated for all the positions in the x-axis of half-broad beans except at 0 (center), 1 (edge) and 1.1 (outside) and for every moment except initial and final times.

2.2.3.1 x-axis in the half-broad bean

The retraction of the matter that is of the order of 25% on the totality of drying, cannot be neglected when computing the coefficients. Indeed, in figure1 (below), the x-axis represents the half bean, in a referential. Whatever is the average content of water, the representative average broad bean is cut up in 5 slices in its half-thickness. Measurements of water content are deferred to the center of each plate. Figure 1 shows the 5 plates and the point of the plate where measurements are deferred. It appears that the points of measurement are equidistant and that the distance which separates them is given by

$e(\bar{X})/10$. If by the thought, one cuts out broad bean in n plates, $e(\bar{X})/2n$ is the step length on the x -axis see the Figure1 below.

2.2.3.2 Calculation of the gradient

Let us note $\frac{\partial X}{\partial x}(x, t)$ the gradient of the function X at the point (x, t) : Let us consider $P(x, t)$ the polynomial function of degree 2 which approach in a least squares sense the five values $X(x - 2dx, t)$, $X(x - dx, t)$, $X(x, t)$, $X(x + dx, t)$, and $X(x + 2dx, t)$. We have:

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial x}(x, t) \approx \frac{\partial P}{\partial x}(x, t)$$

The gradient is calculated neither at the centre nor at the edge. However the assumption of null gradient in the centre makes it possible to calculate the gradients at the points of x -coordinates 0.1 and 0.9. The calculation of $\frac{\partial A}{\partial x}(x, t)$ is done in a similar way.

2.2.3.3 Computation of flows

Let us calculate $m_e(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^x \rho_s(X) \cdot X dx$

Let us consider $P(x, t)$ the polynomial function of degree 2 which approach in a least-squares sense the five values $\rho_s(X(x \pm 2dx, t)) \cdot X(x \pm 2dx, t)$, $\rho_s(X(x \pm dx, t)) \cdot X(x \pm dx, t)$, and $\rho_s(X(x, t)) \cdot X(x, t)$,

Let us note $Q(x, t) = \int_0^x P(\tau, t) d\tau$

This sum represents the quantity of water in this interval delimited by 0 (center of the bean) and the x -coordinate.

Figure1: Schematization of the construction of the x -coordinates of measurement in function of the average content

Let us consider $PP(x, t)$ the polynomial function of degree 2 which approach in a least-squares sense the five values $Q(x, t \pm 2dt)$, $(x, t \pm dt)$, and $(x, t + dt)$.

One has:
$$m_e(x, t) \approx \frac{\partial PP}{\partial t}(x, t)$$

At the initial and final time, flows are not calculated. On the other hand, with the first and with before last moment, the polynomials are adjusted by using only 3 points.

The calculation of $m_a(x, t) \approx \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^x \rho_s(X) \cdot Adx$ is done in a similar way.

2.2.4 Partial pressures of vapour of water and acid

We have already emphasized that at the thermodynamic equilibrium we have $p_e^* = p_e^*(X, A)$ and $p_a^* = p_a^*(X, A)$. Thanks to the use of polynomial functions of degree 2 above we set the following non-linear approximation of p_e^* , (respectively of p_a^*):

$$p_e^*(x, t) = a_1X^2 + b_1A^2 + c_1XA + d_1X + e_1A + f_1 \quad (26)$$

$$p_a^*(x, t) = a_2X^2 + b_2A^2 + c_2XA + d_2X + e_2A + f_2 \quad (27)$$

where the following coefficients obtained by using the least squares method:

$$a_1 = 1.2423e + 005, \quad b_1 = 6.3033e + 008, \quad c_1 = -9.6439e - 006,$$

$$d_1 = -1.8988e + 004, \quad e_1 = 1.4380e + 006, \quad f_1 = -1.2820e + 003$$

$$a_2 = -4.2852, \quad b_2 = -5.8023e + 004, \quad c_2 = 2.1242e + 003$$

$$d_2 = -7.3453, \quad e_2 = 257.0816, \quad f_2 = -0.0577,$$

The partial pressures p_e^* and p_a^* of test 1 are represented by Figure 6.

2.2.5 Partial derivative of the partial pressures

By derivation of the relations (23) and (24), one arrives at:

$$\frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial X}(x, t) = 2a_1X(x, t) + c_1X(x, t) + d_1$$

$$\frac{\partial p_e^*}{\partial A}(x, t) = 2b_1A(x, t) + c_1X(x, t) + e_1$$

$$\frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial X}(x, t) = 2a_2X(x, t) + c_2X(x, t) + d_2$$

$$\frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial A}(x, t) = 2b_2A(x, t) + c_2X(x, t) + e_2$$

2.2.6 Phenomenological coefficients K_{aa} , K_{ae} , and K_{ee}

The relations (23), (24), and (25) and the numerical strategy presented at the subsections 2.2.3, 2.2.4, and 2.2.5 above allow to compute the coefficients K_{aa} , K_{ae} , and K_{ee} .

2.2.7 Transport coefficients D_a , D_{ae} , and D_e

Thank to the relations (19) and (20) we have the following linear system:

$$m_e = D_e \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + D_{ea} \frac{\partial A}{\partial x}$$

$$m_a = D_{ae} \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + D_a \frac{\partial A}{\partial x}$$

By combining with the numerical technique presented at the subsections 2.2.3, 2.24, and 2.2.5 above allow to compute the coefficients D_a , D_{ae} , and D_e .

3 Results and comments

3.1 Results

We present in this part the curves the coefficients of the transportation and the phenomenological coefficients of water and acid in the course of the drying of the cocoa broad bean.

3.1.1 Experimental profiles and Smoothing

Figure 2: Experimental profiles (test 1)

Figure 3: Smoothing of the experimental profiles (test 1)

Figure 4: Smoothing of the kinetics (test 1)

Figure 5: Profiles smoothed with each 3h of drying (test 1)

3.1.2 Curves of partial pressure of acid and water

Figure 6: Curves of partial pressures

3.1.2 Curves the coefficients of the transportation and the phenomenological coefficients of water and the acid following five tests

Tests	Temperature	RH	V(m/s)
1	40	70	0.5
2	40	75	0.5
3	40	85	0.5
4	50	35	0.5
5	50	45	0.5

Table 1: Conditions of drying

Test 1

Test 2

Test 3

Test 4

C

Test 5

3.2 Interpretation

The results of test1, test2, and test4 are similar: the coefficients D_a , D_{ea} and D_e and their corresponding K_{aa} , K_{ea} and K_{ee} decrease as a function of time and therefore influence the water and acid content which also decrease as a function of time. These results show that the water and acid content decrease over time into the cocoa bean during the drying process. On the other hand, we note that D_a and D_{ea} are increasing as a function of space, therefore the acetic acid in the bean is more concentrated in the center than at its edge which has an effect on the decrease in the content in acid depending on the parameter x . The coefficient D_e and K_{ee} have opposite variations but the order of magnitude of D_e imposes its behavior on the water content which decreases as a function of the abscissa x . At the level of test3, we observe that D_a , D_{ea} and D_e are increasing and this can be justified by the high level of relative humidity (85%). We note that under these same conditions the drying time (45 hours) did not significantly reduce the acid and water in the bean. For the test5 we observe that the curves of the coefficients D_a , D_{ea} and D_e decrease with time and this justifies the reduction of the water content and the acid content in the cocoa broad bean during drying. In addition, the curve of D_a decreases when the x -coordinate of half-broad bean decreases. This means that the acid content diminishes gradually from the center of the broad bean towards the edge. On the other hand, the curve of D_e increases at each moment according to the x -coordinate of half-broad bean, therefore the water content decreases gradually from the edge towards the center of broad bean.

5 Conclusion

The mathematical model of the coupled transport of water and acid in a representative average bean in convection mode provides a valuable avenue for numerical simulations on computers and therefore allows a good understanding of kinetic behaviors and interactions at the inside the cocoa bean. However, such a level of performance is only

possible if an efficient characterization of the phenomenological coefficients and the transport coefficients is available. Our work reveals that the absolute values of D_a , D_{ea} and D_e are respectively of the order of 10^{-4} , 10^{-6} , and 10^{-8} (Kg/m.s) while the absolute values of K_{aa} , K_{ea} and K_{ee} are of the order of 10^{-8} , 10^{-12} , and 10^{-11} (kg.s.°C/m³). In addition, the transport coefficients and the corresponding phenomenological coefficients have the same direction of variation with respect to time. Better yet, when the temperature satisfies $40 \leq T \leq 50$, with a relative humidity $35 \leq RH \leq 75$, the transport coefficients are decreasing as a function of time and when the relative humidity is greater than 85%, they are increasing. It therefore appears that the reduction in the water content, then in acid content as a function of time and from the center of the broad bean towards the edge of the bean is generally linked to the decrease with respect to time in the transport coefficients during the drying process.

6 References

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